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Evaluation Of Unemployment And Insecurity In Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Crime instills fear into the populace and causes unnecessary pain, agony, loss of lives and properties. It is also a threat to the security and stability of society. Inability to be gainfully engaged has turned many youths to devil's workshop. In modern times, various movements seek to apply militancy as a solution, or use militancy to rationalize their solutions for issues. Kidnapping, insurgency, militancy is high in the Niger Delta. To tackle insecurity, a key start point should be to understand the causes of insecurity as well as to investigate their sources of social disorder and instability. To address these pressing issues effectively, policymakers and local authorities must prioritize job creation, economic diversification, and conflict resolution strategies to promote stability and prosperity in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area and by extension, Rivers State as a whole.

Keywords: Insecurity, unemployment, human resources

INTRODUCTION

The heightened rate of crime in Nigeria in recent times is worrisome and disturbing. This is evident in daily news report of various crime such as robbery, pilfering, burglary, car theft, rape, kidnapping, internet scam and other social media crimes. Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA, in the yesteryear, was known for peaceful and tranquil atmosphere with adequate protection of lives and properties but in recent times, the spate of crime has taken another dimension (Ibrahim, 2019). For instance, Ahoada-Omoku routes have become endangered routes for travelers as many have fallen victims of kidnap or robbery along these routes (Ibrahim, 2019).

Unfortunately, youths who are more than half of Nigeria's population as t 2016 census (Mbachu & Alake, 2016) and the energetic class, who should diversify their strengths to the development of the country, are often found culpable in the challenge of crimes confronting the LGA and State.

To Adebayo (2013), crime is a threat to the fabric of society. It instills fear into the populace and causes unnecessary pain, agony, loss of lives and properties. It's also at a threat to the security and stability of society. Crimes must be reduced drastically for any country to enjoy sustainable security. Many scholars have attributed the heightened crime rate among youths in Nigeria to unemployment. Indeed, chronic youth employment is evident in thousand of graduate youths produce ever year with no jobs for majority of them (Adebayo, 2013; Ajaegbu, 2012, Kostadis, 2017). Inability to be gainfully engaged has turned many youths to devil's workshop. Adebayo (2013) observed further that most Nigerian youths are either underemployed or unemployed. As a result, some of them opt to perpetrate various crimes.

Unemployment is one of the major challenges in Nigeria today. In spite of thousands of graduates produced every year and an abundance of natural and human resources, the rate of unemployment is increasing at an alarming rate daily. Kazeem (2016) revealed that Nigerian tertiary education

institutions produce up to 500,000 graduates every year besides Nigerian graduates who study abroad and return home to compete for jobs (Kazeem, 2016). The federal tax agency in November, 2016 received 700,000 applications for 500 advertised positions. In May, nearly a million people applied for 10,000 listed positions in the Nigerian by the authors; licensee Online Academic Press, USA Police force (Kazeem, 2017). Voice of America (2018) reported Nigeria's unemployment official figure to be 16 million with additional 2 million expected to join by the end of the year 2018. Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) recorded 14.2% level of unemployment in the last quarter of 2016 compared to 13.9% in the proceeding quarter (Kazeem, 2017).

According to Trading Economic (2019) unemployment rate increased to 23.10 percent in the third quarter from 22.70 percent in the second quarter of 2018. The unemployment rate in Nigeria averaged 12.31 percent between 2006 and 2018, reaching an all high time of 23.10 percent in the third quarter of 2018. The lowest record was 5.10 percent in the fourth quarter of 2010 (Akwagiyam, 2018; Trading Economics, 2019). The growing rate unemployment in Nigeria, especially among the youths is a major challenge to national security.

The high unemployment rate among youths in Nigeria, especially in Rivers State has been attributed to many factors including rapid rural urban migration, rapid population growth, inappropriate school curricula, corruption, decline of the manufacturing sector, perception of policy makes and the youth themselves on employment and poor governance (Adebayo, 2013; Ekeji, 2019). There is a consensus among scholars that joblessness is connected to criminality. Ehrlich cited in Jelilov and Ndanitsa (2015) noted that joblessness is connected with offence because the time spent for genuine work decreases the chance of illegal work. Decrease in unemployment, according to Fadaei-Tehrani and Green in Jelilov and Ndanita (2015) leads to decrease in crime and vice versa. UN-Habitat discovered that socio-economic inequality and lack of opportunity for social advancement and employment are some of the root causes of crime and violence (Ajaegbu, 2012). On the other hand, most of the crimes such as robbery, kidnapping, thuggery and others are characterized with violence and endanger the security of the victims and the society. It is against this background that this study examined unemployment and insecurity in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The spate of crime in communities in Rivers State has literally halted economic and community development efforts and projects in recent years. Notably, the incessant killings, kidnapping, armed robbery, cultist activities and electoral violence recorded in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area has left this area in desolation as most of the community members have fled the community for fear of losing their lives. This situation has also resulted in the abandonment of projects carried out by the people. For example, the building of a youth centre in Obohia Road in Omoku which was initiated by the community to promote youths activities has been abandoned halfway due to consistent violence perpetrated by the youths in this area.

Similarly, the Omoku market in Egbada Road was also abandoned due to consistent killing and factional political violence. In the same line, insecurity issues in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area especially violence and killings emanating from clashes of rival cult groups and politically motivated killings have affected development efforts in this LGA to a great extent.

The effect of crime to socio-economic development were clearly highlighted by Imhabekhai (2009) when he asserted that no meaningful development can take place in a crises prone community. This is because development can only thrive in a peaceful environment. Also, energy and resources of the community would be dissipated towards crises management. Resources that should have been used in providing the much needed goods and services for the people are used in fighting insecurity situations. Cooperation, highly desirable in socio-economic development is often absent among the people since hatred, mistrust, and hostility reign in the community. It is against this problems stated above that the study examined the effects of unemployment and insecurity on community development in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State with the aim of proffering measures to get out of this mess.

Conceptual of Unemployment

The International Labour Organization (ILO) defines the unemployed as the number of all economically active population who are without work but are available for and seeking work,

including people who have voluntarily left work (World Bank, 1998) as cited on Onwuka, Ugwu and Chukwuma (2015). But for Fajana (2009), unemployment refers to a situation where people who are willing and capable of working are unable to find suitable paid employment. This is one of the macro-economic problems that every responsive and sensitive government is expected to be observing and regulating. Furthermore, the higher the unemployment rate in an economy, the higher the poverty level and associated welfare challenges.

According to Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010) and Okafor (2011) showed that Nigeria has a youth population of 80 million, representing over 60% of the total population of the country. The statistics showed that 64 million are unemployed, while 1.6 million are under-employed. Corroborating this, Adebayo (2013) posit that between 1990-2000 data on youth unemployment showed that the largest groups of the unemployed is the secondary school leavers, also 40% of the unemployment rate is among the urban youth aged between 20-24 and 31% of the rate is among those aged 15-19. Two third of the urban unemployed according to the statistics range from 14-24 years.

However, five types of unemployment have been identified by Alao (2005) and Fajana (2000). These include seasonal, residual, structural and open unemployment. Seasonal unemployment is that type experienced as a result of seasonal variation in the activities of particular industries caused by the nature of such industries. Seasonal oriented industries are bound to give rise to seasonal unemployment. The residual unemployment is caused by personal factors such as old age, physical or mental disability, poor work attitudes and inadequate training. Frictional unemployment is caused by industrial friction in which job may exist but the workers may not possess the needed skill for the job or because they are not aware of the existence of the jobs. Such workers include the farmers who use hoes and machetes and are displaced by the introduction of modern equipment. Structural unemployment is that type of unemployment which occurs when there is change in the industry's structure or the economic activities of the country. This happens due to the deficiency of capital resources in relation to demand. The last is the open unemployment and it's the type where there are categories of young men and women who are roaming the streets looking for jobs, but there is no job for them to do and they refused to do the job they see because of certain reasons best known to them (Alao, 2005; Fajana, 2000).

Concept of insecurity

There is a diverse approach to conceptualizing security which is the antithesis of security issues. This study thus seeks to evaluate the concept of security to enhance a good comprehension of the concept of security. Security need was the foundation of the social contract between the people and the state, in which people willingly relinquish their rights to an organ of government that oversees the survival of all sundry. In this circumstance, security embodies the mechanism put in place to eschew, prevent, limit, or resolve violent conflicts, and threats that originate from other states, non – state actors, or structural sociopolitical and economic conditions (Stan, 2004).

For decades, issues relating to security were on the front burner in the development discourse, several efforts have been made since the cold war ended to redefine the concept of security from a state – centric perspective to a broader view that places a premium on individuals, in which human security that embodies elements of national security, human rights and national development remains a major instrument for explaining the concept. At the core of this debate, there has been an effort to deepen and widen the concept of security from the level of the states to societies and individuals, and from military to non – military issues (Nwanegbo and Odigbo, 2013; Kruhmman, 2003).

According to Nwanegbo and Odigbo (2013), as used in Olabanji and Ese, the diverse approaches to the conceptualization of human security in the theoretical literature can be categorized into two major strands. One is a neo – realist theoretical strand that conceptualizes security as the primary responsibility of the state. The Second strand, a postmodernist or plural view, conceptualizes security as the responsibility of non – state and displaces the state as a major provider of security. In Nigeria, the state actors and non – state actors are both stakeholders in the fight against insecurity and the social and economic development of the state. Proponents of the pluralist approach argue that the concept of security goes beyond a military determination of threats. They are of the view that government should be more concerned with the economic security of individuals than the security of the state because the root causes of insecurity are economic. Some scholars in conceptualizing

security emphasized the absence of threats to the peace, stability, national cohesion, and political and socio-economic objectives of a country (Igbuzor, 2011; Oche, 2001; Nwanegbo and Odigbo, 2013) as cited in Olabanji and Ese. Thus, there is a consensus in the contemporary literature that security is essential for national cohesion, peace and sustainable development, it is, therefore, apparent that national security is a desire, sine qua non for the economic growth and development of any country (Oladeji & Folorunso, 2007).

To Adeleke (2013), security implies freedom from threat or violence which could result in the loss of lives and valuable properties. From this viewpoint, security is a situation where one or then generality of the people are from all forms of fears or threats to their precious lives and hard-earned valuables (properties).

Forms of Insecurity in Rivers State

1. Militancy

Various definitions had been given to the term militancy. The word “militancy” can be understood as the acts of individuals, groups or parties displaying or engaging in violence, usually for a cause, whether religious, political, ideological, economic, or social. Nowadays, the term militant is synonymously used with the term terrorist (Quamruzzaman, 2010). Militancy is a state or condition of being combative or disposed to fight for a cause of belief (Chindah & Braide, 2000). It has also been defined as a violent response by an individual, group or sect in a region, community, state or nation due to claims of underdevelopment, political oppression, religious beliefs and segregation. According to Ashimolowo and Odiachi (2012) the motive is that people want their rights and if they are not going to get it by negotiation, they simply will then have it by violence against the “power that be” Hornby (2009) defined militia as an organized group of people comparable to a military force. Quamruzzaman (2010) was of the view that the contemporary sense of the term militia as “paramilitary force motivated by religious or political ideology, especially one that engages in rebel or terrorist activities in opposition to a regular army” is associated with the US usage in the early 1990s as applied to a number of rightwing groups opposed to gun control and distrustful of the federal government. In modern times, various movements seek to apply militancy as a solution, or use militancy to rationalize their solutions for issues. But these movements do not share common tactics. Usually, a militant uses violence as part of a claimed struggle against oppression. Quamruzzaman (2010) stated that a militia movement has five dimensions ideology, motivation, mobilization, organization and ritual. This word is sometimes used to describe anyone with strongly held views (e.g., militant Christian, militant atheist). A militant person or group expresses a physically aggressive posture while in support of an ideology or a cause. A militant person is confrontational regardless of physical violence or pacifistic methods.

2. Kidnappings

Kidnapping is defined by various scholars with varying degree of successes. Firstly, Inyang and Abraham (2013) defined it as “the forcible seizure, taking away and unlawful detention of a person against his/her will. It is a common law offence and by Fage and Alabi (2017) who conceived kidnapping as “forceful or fraudulent abduction of an individual or a group of individuals for reasons ranging from economic, political, and religious to (struggle for) self-determination”. However, the authors later admitted that the forcefully or fraudulently abducted individuals are carried off as hostages for ransom purposes. This implies that while political and economic factors can instigate kidnapping, the economic reason is the most common predisposing factor of the phenomenon. Uzorma and Nwanegbo-Ben (2014, p.132) also defined kidnapping as the “act of seizing and detaining or carrying a person by unlawful force or by fraud, and often with a demand for ransom. It involves taking a person from their family forcefully without their consent with the motive of holding the person as a hostage and earning of profit from their family”. From the foregoing, the definition of kidnapping has no one best way to describe it, but it is clear that for an act to be deemed kidnapping, it shall involve coercive movement of a victim from one place to another, detention or seizure of that person be it a child or an adult. That is why Inyang and Abraham (2013) added that it is legally regarded as a restriction of someone else’s liberty which violates the provision of freedom of movement as enshrined in the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria, where every other law takes its cue from. Kidnapping is on the increase in Nigeria statistically, Nigeria records more than

1,000 kidnapping incidents a year, and there are undoubtedly many that are unreported (Catlin Group, 2012). The British government has decried the fact that at least 25 British and dual British citizens and more than 200 other foreign nationals who have been kidnapped in the Niger Delta area since January 2007 alone. That is why Fage and Alabi (2017) recognized that one of the elements of militancy and/or insurgency in the Niger Delta is kidnapping.

Armed Robbery

Empirical studies have called into question the strength, the significance and the hypothetical relationship between unemployment and crime. The theoretical basis of the debate relies on two countervailing effects of unemployment on crime, that is, a positive motivational effect and a negative opportunity effect. However, the strength and significance of the unemployment and crime relationship in empirical studies have also been shown to be conditional on indicational factors of measurement involving agates. Thus, the direction of the relationship between unemployment and crime is still disputed among scholars. Reilly and Witt (1992) believe the existence of a causal relation between unemployment and armed robbery has been a subject of some investigation in the past. In fact, citations in Field (1990:10) and Timbrell (1990) reveal that such investigation dates as far back as the first century. For instance, Falk and Zweimuller (2005) found a significant positive relationship between state level unemployment and the incidence of right-wing extremist armed robbery in Germany. Fougere and Kramarz (2009) also gained support for the positive relation between unemployment and armed robbery using regional level data for 95 departments of metropolitan France.

Similarly, Baharom and Habibullah (2009:3), using bounds test, found that, in the long run, strong economic performances (real income per capita), indeed, have a positive impact on armed robbery.

Sources of Insecurity in Rivers State, Nigeria

To tackle insecurity, a key starting point should be to understand the causes of insecurity as well as to investigate their sources of social disorder and instability. As Andrew and Kennedy (2003) point out, it is necessary to distinguish between different causes as each may require different remedy. Besides, it is to provide a holistic view to the suggestion or recommendations of solutions. More often, however, policy makers are disinclined to isolate and clarify particular causes. They prefer blanket references, with the consideration that the causes of insecurity are interwoven and contributory to one another. Like in many other societies, the sources of insecurity in Nigeria have been traced to a number of factors and explained by different people. These factors have been classified or grouped into external and internal factors. Beyond the external-internal dichotomy, sources of insecurity have also been classified as either remote or proximate and immediate sources/causal factors.

In Nigeria, the challenge is not so much about insecurity of external sources, but rather that of internal sources. Hence, our focus in this study is on the internal sources. We recognize that some internal factors have been enhanced and strengthened by the presence of external forces, but, there is no doubt that, if the internal situations did not present themselves, the external forces would be unable to infiltrate. We present the internal causes of insecurity in Rivers State using the dichotomy of remote and immediate factors.

- **High Unemployment Rate:** This also explains the genesis of crisis in various community in Rivers State. The youths who are supposed to engage in meaningful activities through acquiring job are left out without employment. This is in conformity with Diara (2010), Ejibunu (2007), and Enyidah-Okey and Ordu (2017), who observed and stated that high degree of unemployment among youths is one of the causes of community crisis, insecurity and social vices. The continuous unemployment exclusion or denial has contributed to youth looking for survival (Best, 2006). Their quest to survive have encouraged crisis in the community through their formation of various cult group, and also alliance to those who struggle for chieftaincy tussle.

- **Loss of Socio-cultural and communal value system:** The traditional value system of the Nigerian society like most African societies is characterized by endearing features as collectivism, loyalty to authority and community, truthfulness, honesty, hard work, tolerance, love for others, Mutual harmony and coexistence, and identification of individual with one another (Clifford, 2009). Other distinctive features of Nigerian traditional society are abhorrence for theft and high value for

live Stealing was considered extremely disgraceful and lives were also highly valued. All of these values which made society secured and safe have all gradually been thrown away and lost. New values have taken over their place over the years, with the so called 'modernity and civilization'. All our endearing values and morals have been trade off for western values. The importance of a people's value system to their survival was espoused by Obama, when he challenged all societies to go back to their traditional values. In his words, cited by Clifford (2009), "Our challenges may be new. The instrument with which we meet them may be new. But those values upon which our success depends are hard work and honesty, courage and fair play, tolerance and curiosity, loyalty and patriotism, these things are old. These things are true. They have been the quick force of progress throughout our history, what is demanded then is a return to these truths.

- **Porous border:** One major immediate factor which has enhanced insecurity in Nigeria is the porous frontiers of the country, where individual movements are largely untracked. The porosity of Nigeria's borders has serious security implications for the country. Given the porous borders as well as the weak and security system, weapons come easily into Nigeria from other countries. Small Arms and Light Weapons proliferation and the availability of these weapons have enabled militant groups and criminal groups to have easy access to arms (Hazen and Horner, 2007). Nigeria is estimated to host over 70 percent of about 8 million illegal weapons in West Africa (Edeko, 2011). Also, the porosity of the Nigerian borders have made it possible for unwarranted influx of migrants from neighbouring countries such as Republic of Niger, Chad and Republic of Benin (Adeola & Oluyemi, 2012). These migrants which are mostly young men are some of the perpetrators of crime in the country.
- **Rural/Urban Drift:** The migration of jobless youths from rural areas to urban centres is also one of the causes of insecurity in Nigeria (Onuoha, 2011). Nigeria is one of the countries in the world with very high rural/urban drift. Most urban areas in Nigeria have grown beyond their environmental carrying capabilities and existing infrastructure and this has resulted to increased poor quality of the living conditions in urban areas in Nigeria (Adedeji & Eziyi, 2020). Out of frustration, these youths are drawn into crime.
- **Unemployment/Poverty:** As a result of the high level of unemployment and poverty among Nigerians, especially the youths, they are adversely attracted to violent crime (Adagba, et a, 2012). Nwagbosa (2012) argued that the failure of successive administrations in Nigeria to address challenges of poverty, unemployment and inequitable distribution of wealth among ethnic nationalities is one of the major causes of insecurity in the country.

Effects of Insecurity in Nigeria

The effects of insecurity on socio-economic development in any society-developed, developing and underdeveloped are not palatable. Some of these effects includes, but not limited to, loss of lives and properties, socio-economic stagnation, social tension, among others. However, Nigeria had established security agencies to combat crime and insecurity, which are the National Security Agency (NSA), the National Intelligence Agency (NIA), the State Security Services (SSS), the Nigeria police Force (NPE), the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS), the Nigeria Customs Service (NCS), the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), and the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC). Still the level of insecurity is on the increase (Nwokwu & Ogayi, 2021).

Violence in its ramification as claimed several lives and properties in Nigeria. Farmers are afraid to farm due to unsolicited attack by the Fulani herdsmen, there is lack of investment confidence, social and economic activities were grouped, schools were closed, and businesses we shut down resulting from Boko Haram activities in the Northern Nigeria. The while, the Southern Nigeria also witness low investment due to the activities of militia groups leading to a decline of investment and economic growth, thereby, increasing the level of unemployment. Interestingly, the government of Nigeria has devoted attention to combating insecurity (Nwokwu & Ogayi, 2021).

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